

UDC 616.31-002.157.2: 616.61-036.12: 616.98-07

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE DIAGNOSIS OF PATHOLOGY OF CHRONIC RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS IN PATIENTS WITH INFECTIOUS PATHOLOGIES OF THE GENITOURINARY SYSTEM

¹Gafforov Sunnatullo Amrulloevich, ²Abdullaev Shokir Ruzievich¹Doctor of Medical Sciences Professor, Head of the Department of Dentistry
Pediatric Dentistry and Orthodontics Tashkent Institute of Advanced Medical Studies²Assistant of the Department of Dentistry Pediatric Dentistry and Orthodontics Tashkent Institute of Advanced
Medical Studies

AbdullayevShokirruziyevich@yandex.ru

Received: 16 March 2020 Revised and Accepted: 16 June 2020

Abstract – CRAS is a fairly common pathology. In recent years, there has been a steady increase in the development of complications of this disease. All patients showed violations of the immunological status of local and general nature, correlating with the severity of the clinical course of the disease [4, 8, 9, 10, 2, 12, 14].

Key words: Oral cavity, urogenital system, immunofluorescence, enzyme immunoassay, chronic renal failure, opportunistic pathogens, interleins.

I. Introduction

Today there are many views of the development of CRAS; the author notes (L.N. Maksimovskaya (1992)) in almost all patients with CRAS, foci of chronic infection of ENT organs are detected; another author [32] notes that the histamine and urea content in the oral fluid (RJ) in patients with CRAS increases with a significant decrease in lysozyme activity, advocates the allergic nature of CRAS about the role of the herpes simplex virus as a lesion of the oral mucosa (CRS) in CRAS [4, 7, 15].

It is believed that, in the pathogenesis of CRAS, great importance is attached to disruption of the vitamin balance, in particular, vitamins B1, B2, B6, B12, hypovitaminosis C [4, 7, 17, 18, 19, 22, 23]; also, with CRAS, a relationship was established between the violation of the biocenosis of SOPR, nose and intestines [4, 7, 16, 33, 34]. In addition, there is information about the role of the cross-immune response in the etiology of CRAS to CRM and in the intestine there are bacterial flora and antibodies [1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 13, 14]

II. Literature review

According to modern concepts, the leading concept of CRAS etiopathogenesis is the immune theory of the development of the disease, which allows the appearance of pathological elements to be associated with a violation of cellular and humoral immunity, both local and general [3, 5, 20];

The aim of the study was to study the condition of the oral cavity with CRAS against the background of the pathology of urinary infections and evaluate the effectiveness of diagnostic methods.

We studied 180 patients aged 25 to 45 years, suffering from CRAS (mild to moderate), COP of them 120 against the background of chronic inflammatory pathology of the urogenital system (group 1) and those suffering from CRAS without urinary tract systems (2nd group).

All patient information on anamnestic data; when applying for dental and urological complaints, it was entered in the form No. 043 / of the medical record of a dental patient with special data developed including information about urogenital tracts. All pathologies were diagnosed using ICD-S based on ICD-10 (1997). Dental research methods; determined the intensity of dental caries, hygienic state of PR (according to the method of J.C. Green, J.R. Vermillion, 1964 evaluated the intensity of the carious process (CPU and PEC); determination of a complex periodontal index (KPI according to P.A. Leus, 1988), saliva viscosity was determined (N.V. Gracheva, 1999), and with the help of a macroluminescent lamp they examined SOP and made a final diagnosis.

An enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was used in the studies; real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR); direct immunofluorescence reaction (PIF) produced the collection of epithelial cells from the urogenital tract, blood and RG. The immune status was assessed by the total number and phagocytic activity of leukocytes (according to the method of J. Wibran, Y. Funderberg (1973)) as well as immunoglobulin in the saliva and serum blood of IgA, IgM, IgG (according to the method of Mancini G. et al., (1965)) We also studied the glucose content, total protein and their fractions, SIgA, the balance factor of local defense factors (Ksb), the activity of alkaline phosphatase (ALP), the amount of total calcium, the concentration of inorganic phosphorus and color reaction with the o-cresolphthalene complex; Hess) in serum an Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out on a computer using the Microsoft Office (Excel) application programs, the statistical programs package “Statgraphics v.7”, “Stadia” and “Statistica 7.0”.

III. Analysis

According to pathologies of PR in the examined group 1 was found - KPU decompensated - 0; KPU, subcompensated form - 1 (0.8%); KPU, compensated form - 3 (2.5%); partial tooth loss - 48 (40.0%); occlusion pathology - 29 (24.1%); pathological abrasion - 13 (10.8%); local hypoplasia - 2 (1.6%); wedge-shaped defect - 44 (36.6%); periodontal disease - 9 (7.5%); catarrhal gingivitis 38 (31.6%); hypertrophic form of gingivitis 13 (10.8%); periodontitis - 33 (27.5%); swelling of the SOPR - 8 (6.6%); dryness, atrophy of SOPR - 5 (4.1%); exfoliative cheilitis - 2 (1.6%); meteorological cheilitis - 9 (7.5%); folded tongue - 6 (5.0%); desquamative glossitis - 5 (4.1%); traumatic erosion - 2 (1.6%); leukoplakia flat - 7 (5.8%); mild leukoplakia - 7 (5.8%); chronic lip crack - 9 (7.5%); lichen planus, typical form - 8 (6.6%); lichen planus, exudative-hypermerized form - 8 (6.6%); herpes - 14 (11.7%); CRAS, Mikulich aphthosis - 90 (75%) and CRAS, Setten aphthosis - 30 (25%). The state of PR in the examined patients is the 2nd group, which complaining with CRAS without pathology of CRF is noted; 0; 0; 1 (1.6%); 25 (41.6%); 15 (25%); 5 (8.3%); 1 (1.6%); 18 (30%); 3 (5.0%); 14 (23.3%); 12 (20.0%); 15 (25.0%); 1 (1.6%); 1 (1.6%); 1 (1.6%); 8 (13.3%); 3 (5.0%); 1 (1.6%); 5 (8.3%); 4 (6.6%); 3 (5.0%); 8 (13.3%); 4 (6.6%); 5 (8.3%); 6 (10%); 0; 0; respectively.

When examining the PR, the aphthae were localized in CRAS in 48% of cases - transitional folds, in 29% of cases - on the lateral surface of the tongue, in 12% of cases - on the CO of the upper and lower lips, in 7% of cases - on the CO of the cheeks, in 2% - on CO of the bottom of the PR, in 1% - in the CO of the retromolar region and in 1% of cases - in the CO of the soft palate; as well as in 59% of cases, the elements of the lesion were localized simultaneously in several sections of the SOPR. Of all patients with aphthous lesions detected, 42% of cases identified small single aphthae from 3-4 mm to 1 cm in diameter (slightly painful, covered with fibrinous coating), in 58% of cases, 2-3 sharply painful when touched, covered with fibrinous coating of aphthae were detected with significant infiltration at the base, from 5 to 11 mm in diameter. $2. \pm 0.1$, in the 2nd group of KPI was 1.42 ± 0.1 As a result of the study, the intensity of dental caries in patients in the 1st group according to the KPI index was 14.61 ± 0.8 ; 2nd group 11.48 ± 0.6 ; The OHI-S index in patients was; 1st group 1.96 ± 0.06 ; 2nd group 2.6 ± 0.08 ; KPI in the 1st group of patients was 1.68 The relationship between CRAS and inflammatory manifestations in the pathology of the urinary system in patients with CRAS compared with the 2nd group ($p \leq 0.01$) were found local clinical manifestations of the inflammatory process in the urinary tract. According to the results of the study, in the process of identifying pathogens, chlamydia by PCR was detected in $49.4 \pm 4.68\%$ of cases, direct immunofluorescence revealed chlamydia in $36.8 \pm 4.84\%$ of cases, and enzyme immunoassay in $26.4 \pm 4.36\%$ of cases.

In patients with CRAS, when tested for chlamydial infection, PCR was the most informative: Napremer, PCR - in 27.3% of cases of chlamydia were found in scrapings from cervix and 26.8% of cases were found in scrapings from the urethra; - Mutual fund - in 5.9% of cases found in scrapings from cervix and 26.9% of cases found in scrapings from urethra; - ELISA - IgG was detected in 16.0% of cases. When ureaplasma is detected, urealitikum by different methods in patients with CRAS - PCR - in $57.4 \pm 2.86\%$ of cases, bacteriological culture on liquid diagnostic environments - in $44.4 \pm 2.67\%$ of cases, and UIF - in $34.8 \pm 6.8\%$ of cases.

Regarding the detection of mycoplasma hominis in patients with CRAS, the best results were shown by the PCR method ($46.2 \pm 2.9\%$ of cases) and bacteriological culture on liquid diagnostic media ($46.0 \pm 2.8\%$ of cases), and the ELISA was on third place ($23.2 \pm 4.0\%$ of cases).

The ELISA method showed a high titer of IgG antibodies in 25% of cases. That is, when detecting mycoplasmal infection, PCR showed the most spectacular results compared to ELISA ($p < 0.01$) and comparable compared to bacteriological culture, bacteriological culture was in second place and ELISA was in third place ($p < 0.01$).

The data obtained at this stage of the work allowed us to choose the real-time PCR method as the main one for the diagnosis of pathogens of urogenital infection in patients with CRAS, but in some cases: with dubious results or as an additional one, we used other existing methods.

We also compared whether the results of the detection of pathogens in the oral fluid are comparable with the detection in other biosubstrates, such as blood and scrapings of the epithelium. As can be seen from table No. 1, the detection of pathogens in the blood is comparable to the detection in mixed saliva ($p = 0.48$). And between the real-

time PCR detection of pathogens in the blood and in scrapings of the epithelium, as in mixed saliva and in the blood, significant differences were found ($p < 0.0001$).

Table №1

Detection of various pathogens of the urinary tract infection with CRAS in biosubstrates by PCR, culture and PIF

Method	Bio substrate	Chlamydia trachomatis		Mycoplasma hominis		Ureaplasma urealitikum	
		+*	-**	+	-	+	-
PCR n-120	Epithelium scraping	100%	0%	100%	0%	100%	0%
	Blood	78±4,47%	22±4,2%	81,2±3,7%	18,8±5,7%	76±4,3%	23±6,3%
	Oral fluid	82±3,2%	17±7,8%	90,8±4,7%	9,9±2,8%	80±5,4%	20±1,4%
Sowing n-120	Scraping epithelium	-	-	100%	0%	90±4,9%	10±2,9%
	Oral fluid	-	-	89,1±6,2%	10,9±5,2%	82±4,9%	18±4,9%
PIF n-120	Scraping epithelium	84±4,0%	16±2,8%	-	-	79±6,0%	21±2,0%
	Oral fluid	62±6,4%	33±4,5%	-	-	66±4,8%	33±3,9%

* "+" - a positive result

** "-" - negative result

The results obtained confirm that, in patients with CKAS, chlamydia trachomatis, ureaplasma urealitikum, and mycoplasma hominis are significantly more likely to be found in scrapings of the epithelium compared with displaced saliva (CC). PCR with approximately the same information content allows you to detect the studied pathogens in the blood and in the SS. In this case, mycoplasma hominis is most effectively diagnosed by all methods. Some recent evidence even suggests that mycoplasma may be part of the normal microflora of PR.

In patients of the 1st group, a case was observed in 120 patients; anxiety in connection with the detection of the causative agent of urinary tract infection - 120; increased emotionality - 45; itching, burning in the urogenital tract: constantly - 9; periodically - 6; as a result of cooling, -45; dysuric symptoms - 20; discharge from the urethra and genital organs -2; pain (constantly -5; sometimes, periodically - 55; spontaneous - 51; joint pain -12); symptoms of asthenia, fatigue and malaise - 13; pustular processes on the skin - 30; allergy -62 cases.

IV. Discussion

At present, laboratory assessment of almost all parts of the immune system associated with SOPR is possible. During an immunological examination of patients with CRAS to determine the presence and severity of immune deficiency, a survey of patients was carried out in order to collect anamnesis and elucidate the clinical signs of the disease; when collecting the anamnesis, it turned out that 76% of patients with CRAS suffer from a syndrome of decreased resistance to various infectious diseases (ARVI, influenza); in 69% of cases there were reducing infectious and inflammatory processes; skin lesions were detected in 19% of patients with CRAS; in 42% of patients with CRAS and urogenital infection, and in 25% of patients with CRAS, arthritis occurred.

The results of the study of leukocytes, lymphocytes, monocytes, segamenuclear and polymyocadic neutrophils, eosonophils, B-lymphocytes and HCT test parameters are shown in table No.2.

The results of leukocytes and lymphocytes in the peripheral blood revealed an increase in their number in the examined groups of patients compared with the 2nd group.

Table №2.

Examined patients with CRAS and the source of infection of the urinary tract ($M \pm m$ in%).

№	Biosubstrates	Amount
1	White blood cell count (normal: $4-9 \times 10^9 / l$)	5,8±0,28* ($p < 0,05$)
2	The number of lymphocytes in the blood (normal: 19-37%)	34,0±0,42*

		(p<0,05)
3	The number of monocytes in the blood (normal: 3-11%)	5,6±0,64 (p<0,05)
4	The number of segmented neutrophils in the blood (normal: 47-72%)	68,4±1,24* (p<0,05)
5	The number of stab neutrophils in the blood (normal: 1-6%)	2,32±0,62* (p<0,05)
6	The number of eosinophils in the blood (normal: 0.5-6%)	1,9±0,44* (p<0,05)
7	The number of b-lymphocytes in the blood (normal: 15-35%)	14,6±0,45* (p<0,05)
8	NCT Test Indicators (normal: 40-80%)	14,8±0,85* (p<0,05)

Appendix: * - statistically significant differences relative to the control group (p <0.05).

In the peripheral blood of patients with CRAS, an increased percentage of monocytes were found or approaching the upper limit of the norm, which may also indirectly indicate the presence of pathology, but so far in the stage of compensation due to the reserve capabilities of the body. Significant differences in indices (p <0.01) were found in the number of stab neutrophil.

We observed the active participation of all immunocompetent cells in the process of chronic inflammation in patients of the 1st group. Among these cells, a special role was played by monocytes involved in the regulation of the immune response, and lymphocytes, which are called key cells of the immune system, but at the same time, we observe different changes in the indicators of the immune status in almost every patient of the 1st group.

According to our data, a chronic inflammatory process associated with the presence of opportunistic pathogens in the RP and urogenital tract may develop in patients with CRAS and the site of infection of the urinary tract. The results indicate that in patients with CRAS against the background of chronic renal failure signs of local immunodeficiency were detected, which is largely determined by the place and prevalence of inflammation.

When analyzing the amount of IgG, we did not find an increase in it, however, in our case, inhibition of the B-cell component of the immune system occurred, since chronic inflammation initiated by urogenital infection developed. The amount of IgG in patients with CRAS against the background of pathology of the urinary tract was 11.2 ± 0.16 g / l compared with the control: 12.8 ± 0.4 g / l (normal: 7.5-15.45 g / l); the IgA content in the 1st group of patients was 2.45 ± 0.48 g / l compared with the control of 1.9 ± 0.08 g / l (normal: 1.25-2.5 g / l).

Table No. 3 shows the results of a study of some immunological as well as biochemical parameters of the composition of the cancer in cases of chlamydia, mycoplasmosis and ureaplasmosis. In the 2nd group, the levels of sialic acids, IgA and IgG, as well as the value of Kcb. in RJ is much lower than in individuals with mycoplasmosis. Analysis of the levels of total calcium, inorganic phosphorus, lysozyme and SigA, as well as alkaline phosphatase activity in the composition of the RG is reduced.

Table №3

Biochemical and immunological parameters of pancreatic cancer in patients with CRAS with ureaplasmosis, chlamydia and mycoplasmosis.

RJ indicators	Ureaplasmosis n = 10	Chlamydia N = 10	Mycoplasmosis N = 10
Alkaline phosphatase, mmol / hr	0,89 ± 0,04*	0,9±0,04*	0,82 ± 0,02*
Sialic acids, units	5,37 ± 0,28*	4,5±0,14*	8,02 ± 0,14*
Total Ca, mmol / L	0,76 ± 0,05*	0,59±0,01*	0,62 ± 0,01*
Inorganic phosphorus, mol / L	2,91 ± 0,13*	2,7±0,39*	3,62 ± 0,37*
IgA, g / l	0,28 ± 0,02*	0,16±0,001*	0,19± 0,001*
IgG, g / l	0,13± 0,005*	0,17±0,002*	0,14± 0,002*

Lysozyme,%	14,9 ± 0,57*	12,42±0,21*	13,91 ±0,14*
SIgA, g / l	0,12 ± 0,04*	0,08±0,004*	0,14± 0,004*
Csb.	2,99 ± 0,26*	5,71±0,02*	3,41 ±0,13*

Appendix: * - statistically significant differences relative to control (p <0.05).

V. Conclusion

Thus, in the examined patients with CRAS on the background of CKD, more often dental problems are found and more severe clinical course pathologies of SOPR: Napremer; in patients of the 1st group, the incidence of caries is 4.8%; OHI-S index is 6.6%; KPI - 5.8% of cases are more common when compared with the 2nd group of patients.

The analysis of the results obtained allows us to conclude that the real-time PCR method is more effective than the other existing methods for the diagnosis of pathogens of urogenital infection in patients with CRAS. Most patients with CRAS and foci of urinary tract infection have sharply immunological signs of exacerbated chronic inflammation. In addition, the prevalence and severity of allergic and autoimmune manifestations in these groups was also significantly higher (p <0.001), compared with the 2nd group. When CRAS and urinary tract infections, immunological signs of exacerbation of chronic inflammation were detected. The main pathogenetic factor in the recurrence of infection with CRAS is immunodeficiency of T-cell and B-cell units, which has individual characteristics and a significant scatter in each patient with CRAS, which causes dysfunctions of polymorphonuclear leukocytes, including the ability to carry out phagocytosis of pathogens, which contributes to their persistence, reproduction and active dissemination by lymphogenous and hematogenous pathways throughout the body. In this case, the most pronounced changes were noted with chlamydia.

VI. References:

1. Borovsky E.V. Therapeutic dentistry: textbook. allowance / ed. E.V. Borovsky. - M.: MIA, 2011. -- 840 p.
2. Buzikashvili N.E. Biomedical statistics: textbook. benefits for studios. universities / N.E. Buzikashvili, D.V. Samoilova; subred S. Glanz; trans. from English Yu.A. Danilova. - M.: Practice, 1998. -- 459 p.;
3. Gileva, O.S. Comprehensive dental rehabilitation of patients with diseases of the oral mucosa: rational approaches to prosthetic treatment / O.S. Gileva [et al.] // Dentistry for all. - 2013. - No. 4. - P. 9-14.
4. Kazarina L.N. Evaluation of the immunological status of the oral cavity in patients with bronchial asthma taking inhaled hormonal drugs / L.N. Kazarina, I.M. Chuvarkova // Periodontology. - 2013. - T. 18. - No. 2. - P. 18-21.
5. Kazarina L.N. The state of periodontal and immune status in children with esophagogastroduodenal pathology / L.N. Kazarina, A.E. Pursanova // Dentistry. - 2010. - T. 89. - No. 2. - P. 15-17.
6. Karpishchenko A.I. Medical laboratory technologies and diagnostics: reference book / ed. A.I. Karpishchenko. - SPb.: Intermedika, 1999. -- 656 p.
7. Rabinovich I.M. Recurrent aphthous stomatitis - etiology of pathogenesis (part I) / I.M. Rabinovich, O.F. Rabinovich, E.L. Panfilova, E.V. Vakhrushina // Dentistry. - Media sphere. - 2010. - 1. - P. 71-74.
8. Serov V.N. Rational therapy of vaginal infections / V.N. Serov // Gynecology. - 2005. - T. 7, No. 2. - P. 115-118
9. Starokozheva L.Yu. Modern cryotechnologies in the complex therapy of chronic aphthae of the oral mucosa / L.Yu. Starokozheva // Siberian Dental Forum: Sat. scientific tr All-Russian scientific and practical conference. - Krasnoyarsk, 2008. -- 266-269 p.
10. Tokmakova S.I. The use of low temperatures to eliminate a pain symptom in chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis / S.I. Tokmakova, L.Yu. Starokozheva, T.N. Ulko // Biocompatible materials with shape memory and new technologies in dentistry: materials of a scientific and practical conference. - Tomsk, 2006. -- 155-158 p.
11. Tokmakova S.I. Methods for assessing the effectiveness of cryo-analgesia of aphthae in the treatment of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis / S.I. Tokmakova, L.Yu. Starokozheva // M., 2008. - Volume 7. - No. 2. - 18-20 p.
12. Fletcher R. Clinical epidemiology. Basics of evidence-based medicine: Trans. from English / R. Fletcher, S. Fletcher, E. Wagner. - 3rd ed. - M.: Media Sphere, 2004. -- 352 p.
13. Aas J.A. Defining the normal bacterial flora of the oral cavity / J.A. Aas, B.J. Paster, L.N. Stokes et al // J Clin Microbiol. - 2005. - 43. - Pp. 5721-5732.
14. Abdo Z. Statistical methods for characterizing diversity of microbial communities by analysis of terminal restriction fragment length polymorphisms of 16S rRNA genes / Z. Abdo, U.M. Schuette, S.J. Bent et al // Environ Microbiol. - 2006. - 8. - Pp. 929-938.
15. Aberdam D. Embryonic stem cells as a cellular model for neuroectodermal commitment and skin formation / D. Aberdam, K. Gambaro, A. Medawar et al // C R Biol. - 2007. - 330. - 479 pp.
16. Abrahamsson T.R. Low diversity of the gut microbiota in infants with atopic eczema / T.R. Abrahamsson, H.E. Jakobsson, A.F. Andersson et al // J Allergy Clin Immunol. - 2012. - 129. - Pp. 434-440.

17. Abashidze N.O. Immunomorphological aspects of the differential diagnosis of recurrent aphthous stomatitis and Setton stomatitis / N.O. Abashidze [et al.] // *Periodontology*. - 2006. - No. 3.- P. 77-86.
18. Aggarwal A. Estimation of serum beta carotene levels in patients with oral submucous fibrosis in India / A. Aggarwal, A. Shetti, V. Keluskar, A. Bagewadi // *J Oral Sci*. - 2011. - 53. - Pp. 427-431.
19. Chiappelli F. Psychobiologic views on stress-related oral ulcers / F. Chiappelli, O.S. Cajulis // *Quintessence Int*. - 2004. - 35. - Pp. 223-227.
20. Ahmed A. Caspase 3 activity in isolated fetal rat lung fibroblasts and rat periodontal ligament fibroblasts: cigarette smoke induced alterations / A. Ahmed, J.A. Thliveris, A. Shaw et al // *Tob Induc Dis*. - 2013. - 11(1). - 25 pp.
21. Ahmed N.N. Acute care for the elderly: a literature review / N.N. Ahmed, S.E. Pearce // *Popul Health Manag*. - 2010. - 13(4). - Pp. 219-225.
22. Albanidou-Farmaki E. Outcome following treatment for *Helicobacter pylori* in patients with recurrent aphthous stomatitis / E. Albanidou-Farmaki, L. Giannoulis, A. Markopoulos et al // *Oral Dis*. - 2005. - 11. - Pp. 22-26.
23. Altinyazar H.C. The status of oxidants and antioxidants in the neutrophils of patients with recurrent aphthous stomatitis / H.C. Altinyazar, A. Gürel, R. Koca et al // *Turkish Journal of Medical Sciences*. - 2006. - 36(2). - Pp. 87-91.
24. Anand V. Low level laser therapy in the treatment of aphthous ulcer / V. Anand, M. Gulati, V. Govila, B. Anand // *Indian Journal of Dental Research*. - 2013. - 24(2). - Pp. 267-270.
25. Arakeri G. Oral submucous fibrosis: an overview of the aetiology, pathogenesis, classification, and principles of management / G. Arakeri, P.A. Brennan // *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. - 2013. - 51. - Pp. 587-593.
26. Arikan S. Oxidant/antioxidant status in recurrent aphthous stomatitis / S. Arikan, C. Durusoy, N. Akalin et al // *Oral Dis*. - 2009. - 15. - Pp. 512-515.
27. Baharvand M. Comparison of burning mouth syndrome prevalence and its related factors between menopausal and non-menopausal women / M. Baharvand, M. Eshghpour, H. Mortazavi, Z. Fallah // *J Dent Mater Tech*. - 2014. - 3. - Pp. 16-22.
28. Batsakis J.G. Proliferative verrucous leukoplakia and its related lesions / J.G. Batsakis, P. Suarez, A.K. el-Naggar // *Oral Oncol*. - 1999. - 35. - Pp. 354-359.
29. Bogefors J. Reduced tonsillar expression of human beta-defensin 1, 2 and 3 in allergic rhinitis / J. Bogefors, A.M. Kvarnhammar, U. Hockerfelt, L.O. Cardell // *FEMS Immunol Med Microbiol*. - 2012. - 65(3). - Pp. 431-438.
30. Boyce S.T. Cultured skin substitutes: a review / S.T. Boyce // *Tissue Eng*. - 1996. - 2. - 255 pp.
31. Savage N.W. Burning mouth syndrome: Clinical presentation, diagnosis and treatment / N.W. Savage, V.V. Boras, K. Barker // *Australas J Dermatol*. - 2006. - 47. - Pp. 77-81.
32. Villa A. Oral cancer and oral erythroplakia: an update and implication for clinicians / A. Villa, C. Villa, S. Abati // *Aust Dent J*. - 2011. - 56. - Pp. 253-256.
33. Cherry A.B. Reprogramming cellular identity for regenerative medicine / A.B. Cherry, G.Q. Daley // *Cell*. - 2012. - 148. - 1110 pp.